

Ion Transport Ability and Selectivity relating to the Structure of Synthetic Ionophores and Effect of Anion

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The transport of alkali metal picrates, 2,4-dinitrophenolates and *ortho*-nitrophenolates through chloroform membrane containing a series of noncyclic oxocrowns as carriers was studied. The properties of complexation and transport are largely dependent on the length of the oxyethylene chain of oxocrowns. The presence of rigid aromatic donor end group affects the selectivity as well as the transport rate. The effect of counter anion on the transport of alkali metal cation was found to be significant.

Transport of cations across a hydrophobic organic layer (liquid membrane) which separates two water phases has attracted recent interest¹. Macrocyclic polyethers have drawn attention in both chemistry and biology to selective complexation of various metal cations^{2,3}. The nature of anion should thus be a factor in determining the rate of cation transport¹. It is known that remarkable conformational changes of natural noncyclic ionophores are induced during ion transport⁴ and are related to the cation. However, the relationship between conformation and cation selectivity of synthetic ionophores has been clarified⁵. Potential applications of this transport technology include the separation and concentration of chemical species, the detection and measurement of chemical species and the removal of undesirable chemical species from the environment or from carrier.

In this study the authors report the synthesis of oligoethylene glycol derivatives containing different end groups, and the effect on anion type on the rate of transport of alkali metal ions using carriers of varying chainlength and both aromatic and non-aromatic donor end groups.

Results and Discussion

The results (Table 1) show that the difference of the transport capability of individual ionophore **1a-c**, **2b** and **2c** for each alkali metal cation seems to be small, while the competitive transport of alkali metal

1a; n = 1
1b; n = 2
1c; n = 3

2b; n = 2
2c; n = 3

ion by these ionophores shows that amount of Li⁺ ion transported is large with **1a**, that of Na⁺ with **1b** and amount of K⁺ ion transported is large with **1c**. This can be explained on the basis of length of oxyethylene chain and size of the cation. It can be proposed that ionophore **1a** needs high conformational changes to adopt pseudocyclic conformation⁷ in order to hold K⁺ ion for transport, while **1c** can easily form a pseudocyclic cavity best fitted to the size of K⁺ ion. Same explanation⁸ can be given for **1a** and **1b** to adopt pseudocyclic conformation according to size of Li⁺ and Na⁺ respectively. As shown in Table 1, the ionophores

2b and **2c** can transport Na^+ and K^+ selectively and produce the largest transport rate among these ionophores, while the ionophores **1a–c** transport Li^+ and K^+ less selectively with smaller transport rate under the same conditions. This may be due to the lesser flexibility of **2b** and **2c** which enhances stability of pseudocyclic conformation to adopt the size of the cation, while **1a–c** are highly flexible and able to transport the cations but to a lesser extent with less selectivity⁹.

Among the three anions Pic^- transfer more rapidly than Dnp^- and Onp^- . In case of Onp^- no transport was observed, this is because the charge on Pic^- anion is more delocalised than Dnp^- and Onp^- and hence is less associated with the cation. The anion desolvation energy barrier is one of the most important factor in controlling the transfer across the membrane. It is noteworthy that the order of anion is same for all five carriers with all salts except that, amount of K^+ transported, changes drastically over large magnitude with picrate as anion.

TABLE I—AMOUNTS OF CATION TRANSPORTED BY THE SYNTHETIC IONOPHORES THROUGH CHLOROFORM LIQUID MEMBRANE AFTER 24 h

Metal salt	Transported cation (%) with				
	1a	1b	1c	2b	2c
LiPic	11.8	9.2	5.1	11.4	12.0
NaPic	7.2	12.1	10.1	44.3	30.2
KPic	3.2	5.2	15.5	38.7	48.2
LiDnp	7.1	6.2	3.0	9.2	10.1
NaDnp	3.2	8.5	6.2	39.5	25.5
KDnp	1.2	2.5	7.3	30.7	40.4

*Reproducibility $\pm 7\%$

In conclusion, these results could give an important suggestions on the designing of molecule of non-cyclic ionophore with ion selectivity. (i) Number of oxyethylene unit affects greatly the selectivity and the transport rate¹⁰. (ii) The ion selectivity of noncyclic ionophore with the same skeleton changed drastically by selection of the two end groups, that is, the introduction of aromatic group is much more effective than that of non-aromatic group. (iii) Thus the magnitude of the effect of anion on the facilitated transport of cations across liquid membrane holds significant im-

portance. The transport of cations across membranes can be turned on or off simply by altering the anion present in source solution. This same anion effect might be useful in separating and detecting anions themselves.

Experimental

All reagents (Fluka) were used without further purification. All metal picrate, dinitrophenolate and *ortho*-nitrophenolates (MPic, MDnp and MOnp) were prepared by adding an equimolar solutions of picric acid, dinitrophenol and *ortho*-nitrophenols in ethanol to an aqueous solution of metal hydroxide¹¹.

The acetoacetate diesters of di-, tri- and tetraethylene glycols (**1a–c**) and ethylbenzoate diesters of tri- and tetra ethylene glycols (**2b, c**) were prepared by the procedure described in the literature¹². These five oxocrowns were used as carrier for transport studies.

A mixture of diethylene glycol (0.66 mol) and ethyl acetoacetate (2 mol) was heated slowly for 3 h at 180^o at atmospheric pressure. During this period ethanol was collected. Once ethanol ceased to distil off, distillation was continued at 20 mm pressure, leading to the collection of excess ethyl acetoacetate (b.p 180^o). The oily residue was analysed: ν_{max} (neat) 3 500 (OH), 1 740 and 1 715 cm^{-1} (C=O); $^1\text{H}_{\text{NMR}}$ δ (CDCl_2) 2.33 (s, 6 CH_3), 3.62 (s, 4 CH_2), 3.80 (m, 4 OCH_2) and the enol at 2.02 (s, 6 CH_3) and 5.18 (s, 2 vinyl H); m/z 274.103 (calcd. for: $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_7$ CH₂ 274.104).

Procedure: The liquid membrane system used was adopted from the work of Kobuke *et al.*¹³. The transportation of alkali metal cations was carried out using apparatus identical with that shown schematically in Fig. 1, where chloroform including synthetic ionophores were employed as liquid membrane. Duplicate measurements were taken for every transport rate determination.

A chloroform layer containing $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ solution of the carrier rested at the bottom. Atop this layer there are two water phases, separated by a glass-cylinder. The inner phase was a salt solution

($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) serving as a cation source and the outer phase was distilled water serving as receiving phase. The three phases were agitated constantly by a magnetic stirrer at 200 rpm for 24 h. The system was sealed to minimise evaporation. The vessel was maintained at $25 \pm 1^{\circ}$ in a thermostated water-bath. Samples were analysed for cation content using a Perkin-Elmer atomic absorption spectrophotometer.

Fig. 1. Liquid membrane cell : (a) source phase, (b) receiving phase, (c) membrane phase, (d) magnetic stirring bar and (e) glass cylinder.

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